

A Middle English Poetics of Experience? The case of *Reson and Sensuallyte*

Welcome - thanks you for the invitation...

So my topic today is 'experience', and I want to take a moment to explain the rationale for my interest, and perhaps the broader context for what I argue is a rapid growth of interest in the notion of experience in Middle English poetry in the period between about 1360 and 1410. So first I want to exemplify (very briefly) the 'experiential turn' in this period - with reference to both Chaucer and Langland. I then want to try and place this in a broader and longer historical and intellectual context. This is actually the really difficult bit... because that context is plural and quite complex: the question of experience demonstrably DOES become a central concern in scholastic debates from the late thirteenth and late fourteenth century (especially in philosophy of mind and epistemology, but also in the natural sciences and in theology), but it seems to me that postulating a direct, linear line of transmission from scholasticism to poetry is rather difficult to substantiate and perhaps somewhat simplistic. So part of my argument will be to claim that in addition to what we might call the 'scholastic context' for this experiential turn in Middle English poetry, we also need to look to earlier literary traditions, and specifically to the francophone tradition of narrative dream-vision allegory that develops in the wake of the hugely influential *Roman de la Rose*. This tradition, however, is itself in dialogue with scholastic intellectual culture, making it extremely difficult to draw a precise and fine-grained picture of how exactly scholastic ideas and debates 'trickle down' into vernacular literary culture. And it is even more difficult to gauge how exactly French and later English vernacular poets respond to those ideas and debates creatively, often at one or two removes, and availing themselves of their 'poetic licence'.

So in the second half of my talk I want to do a bit of a case study, looking at a text that is produced in a slightly later period, in the wake of the 'experiential turn' I have describing, and that in some ways displays a new, modified, and overall more cautious and ambivalent attitude toward the idea of experience. The text is the ME *Reson & Sensuallyte* (around 1410 perhaps), which is a fragmentary translation of the French *Eschez Amoureux*, tentatively attributed to Lydgate.

Just one further caveat perhaps, to avoid muddying an already quite complex issue: 'experience' also is a key notion in late medieval devotional writing, and in earlier traditions of mystical or monastic thought. While debates around specifically 'religious experience' are clearly part of the larger picture, I will put these ideas to one side today, since my focus today is the epistemology of ordinary experience., designating the processes involved in the transition from sensation to cognition in relation to perfectly ordinary everyday objects and situations.

Langland may well be the first recorded author to use the term 'experience' in English, (not in the MED - *Piers Plowman* B. XVIII.151 / C. XX.153; see Langland 2011), and Langland been credited with nothing less than 'the invention of experience as a literary category' in a hugely influential study (by Anne Middleton, 'Narration and the Invention of Experience: Episodic Form in *Piers Plowman*', 1982). Langland also notably assigns a pivotal role to the idiosyncratic notion of 'kynde knowinge' (best translated perhaps as 'practical / natural / experiential understanding', cf. Bose 2018, see further White 1988 and Harwood 1992). So, when Holy Church tells Will to set out on a quest for truth, Will counters that he lacks 'kynde knowinge', and that he needs to be enlightened about how the knowledge of Truth comes to be in his body - his 'cors': **SLIDE 1**

'Forþi I sey as I seide ere, bi sighte of thise textis
Whan alle tresores arne y-tryed, Treuþe is the best.
Lereþ it this lewede men, for lettred men it knowen,
That treuþe is tresore the triest on erthe.'

**Yet have I no kynde knowinge', quod I, 'yet mote ye kenne me better
By what craft in my cors it comseþ and where'.**

PP/B I.134-9

Although Langland here clearly speaks of spiritual /religious experience (not ordinary experience) the crux of the problem is embodiment, or the process through which knowledge comes to be in the individual person, defined as a hylomorphic body-soul compound following Aristotle. This touches on one of the key issues whose resolution continued to elude the efforts of scholastic philosophers as a whole, namely the question of how the mind produces and grasps 'concepts' - or, more prosaically, the question of how 'things' come to be in the mind. This was a massive problem for the scholastics, and threatened to implode the entire system of Aristotelian psychology. According to Peter King "the inability of the scholastic tradition to reach consensus on a response to [the problem of transduction between sense and intellect] eventually led to the wholesale collapse of the Aristotelian approach to the mind" over the course of the *longue durée* from the thirteenth to the seventeenth centuries. I will return to some aspects of this problem shortly...

So, whereas references to the 'experiential' character of Langland's poetry in recent criticism are legion, I confess that I am struck by the reticence of critics to unpack what 'experience' might mean in practice. I don't think this is simply a matter of 'omission' or lack of interest, but rather a result of the complexity of the question itself, and of Langland's refusal (or inability) to define what is meant by experience; this is after all precisely the question that Will asks - and the question is never really answered. The only consolation here is, perhaps, that Will (and Langland) were in very good company...

Turning briefly to Chaucer now. In Chaucer's references to 'experience' and its broader semantic field — including ideas of proof, demonstration, and experimentation — are ubiquitous, or rather endemic (Benson 1991). From 'preven' (e.g. *T&C* I.969, IV.1401, V.676; *HF* 787; *LoGW* 2394; 'MT' 1330) to 'preven by resoun' (*PF* 534), to 'preven by experience' (e.g. *HF* 878; 'ST' 2057; 'KnT' 3001), to 'assayen' (e.g. 'WoB Prol.' 290; *RomRos* B 3449, 3684), 'make assay' (e.g. 'CYT' 1249), or 'preven by assay' (e.g. *BD*, 552 574; *LoGW* Prol. G, 9), and other cognates of 'experience' and 'experiment' (e.g. 'WoB Prol.' 468; *HF* 788; 'CIT' 788; 'FriT' 1517; 'NPT' 2978). Critical accounts of Chaucer's poetry and poetics routinely invoke the binary pair of 'experience and auctoritee', but here too I struggle to get a proper handle on the meaning of 'experience' beyond the fact that it is not a transparent concept or category. Here again I have found next to no trace of any attempts to get under the skin of the notion of 'experience' and its semantic field. The notable exception here is an article by Derek Pearsall, which is a very helpful lexicographical study from which I have drawn a number of ideas..

Just some thoughts on why the question of the 'opacity' of the term 'experience' and its wider semantic field has not received the attention it deserves. This is due in part - but in part only - to our own professional biases. My hunch is that ultimately we — as modern, and understandably text-obsessed literary critics of one kind or another — tend to be drawn to the complexities and slippages of authority, since the latter is inherently subject to interpretation, equivocation, reappropriation. In the process we rather tend to overlook or gloss over the equally opaque nature of 'experience', perhaps because we tacitly assume that we all know what experiences are: we have experiences all the time, and the very 'experiential' character of experience suggests to us that the concept is universal, transhistorical. In short, we assume that *auctoritee* is a historically determined cultural construct, while experience is not.

Despite the lack of sustained critical discussions of the meaning of 'experience' itself in Chaucer's poetry (just as in Langland's), it is fair to say that critics have almost invariably stressed that the apparent opposition of *experience* and *auctoritee* is dismantled and deconstructed in all kinds of complex and interesting ways in Chaucer's poetry. This goes some way towards admitting (albeit only implicitly) that experience is not, after all, a stable and trans-historical category. And Chaucer, it seems to me, makes the point about the entanglements of *experience* and *auctoritee* rather forcefully at times. Just take this example from the Prologue of the *LoGW*. The narrator first expresses his reverence for book learning - but quickly shifts gears to celebrate the even stronger pleasures of nature and springtime **SLIDE 2**

On bokes for to rede I me delyte
 And to hem yive I ful credence,
 And in myn herte have hem in reverence
 So hertely that there is game noon

That from my bookes maketh me goon,
But it be seldom, on the holiday,
Save, certeynly, whan that the month of May
Is comen
LGW (F) 30-37

But of course as soon as the Dreamer/ Narrator sets out into the putatively 'real world' of springtime, he steps into a space that is a nothing if not a literary convention... to 'experience' Nature only vicariously. A similar configuration obtains also in the *House of Fame*: Here Chaucer's dreamer finds himself able to experientially 'preve' the truthfulness ('sooth') of the writings of ancient *auctores* - Boethius, Martianus Cappella, and Alan of Lille. The only problem is that the grounding of this 'proof' is not empirical reality at all, but the narrator's own dream experience: **SLIDE 3**

'I wot wel I am here;
But wher in body or in gost
I noot ywis, but God, thou wost!
For more clere entenement
Nas me never yet y-sent.
And than thoughte I on **Marcian**,
And eek **Anticlaudian**,
That **sooth was hir descripcioun**
Of al the hevenes regioun
As fer as that I sawe the preve.
Therefor I can hem now beleve.
HF 980-90

Significantly Chaucer too - like Langland but in a different context - raises the thorny question of where exactly this kind of experience occurs: is it 'in body' or merely 'in gost', or somewhere across that divide?

Chaucer's point seems to me to be that when all is said and done, the manner in which we *experience* something is substantially co-determined by the impact of *auctoritee* upon our minds - and, conversely, that *auctoritee* or *auctoritates* are in turn 'experienced' by us in some fashion that Chaucer's poetry never quite defines, but nonetheless goes on to illustrate and explore. Take the beginning of the *Book of the Duchess* **SLIDE 4**, where the dreamer finds himself in a 'chaumbre' that features windows representing **hooly al the story of Troye** which **Was in the glasinge y-wrought**. The walls too are 'peynted' with 'both texte and glose / of al the Romance of the Rose'

And, sooth to seyn, **my chambre** was
ful **wel depeynted**, and with glas
Were al the windowes wel y-glased,

Ful clere, and nat an hole y-crased,
 That to beholde it was gret joye.
 For **hooly al the story of Troye**
Was in the glasinge y-wrought thus,
 of Ector and of kinge Priamus,
 Of Achilles and Kinge Lamedoun,
 Of Medea and of Jasoun,
 Of Paris, Eleyne, and Lavyne.
And al the walles with colours fyne
Were peynted, bothe texte and glose,
Of al the Romaunce of the Rose.
 My windowes weren shet echoon,
 And thurgh the glas the sonne shoon
 Upon my bed with bright bemes,
 With many glade gilde stremes
 (Chaucer, *Book of the Duchess*, 321–38)

Clearly the point here is that the dream experience is itself substantially made up of mental objects that have been previously 'abstracted' from pre-existing texts, through an act of imaginative reading, and are now experienced (in a dream) through a process of visual 'embodied simulation' - to borrow a term from present-day research in linguistic neuroscience. *Auctoritee* is made into *experience*, 'thickened' into objects that are visual as well as textual, and the *chaumbre* clearly here functions as an allusion to the *cellula* or *camera* of the imagination, located in one of the brain's ventricles. **Image** This is fairly standard stuff, and typical of Neo-Aristotelian Faculty psychology that was widely accessible, and Chaucer is clearly familiar with the idea and elsewhere refers to the same notion when he mentions the 'Celle Fantastik', in the KnT.

Just a couple of quotes by scholars better placed to make this point....

Already in 1969, Charles Schmitt observed in his analysis of the scientific methodology in Galileo's astronomical writings that the study of Western attitudes to 'experience' was hopelessly hampered by semantic difficulties, and expressed the wish for "a comprehensive study of the changing roles which 'experience' and 'experiment' have played in the development of Western thought, [clarifying] what meanings the terms have taken on under various circumstances, and what relation 'experience' and 'experiment' have had to other sources of knowledge" (Schmitt 1969, 81). The problem persists even fifty years after Schmitt's comment, and more recent commentators have reiterated the need for such a study. So David Lindberg writes (in 2010) that "[t]he subject of [pre-modern] experimentation and its corollary, experimental science, is fraught with semantic difficulties" (Lindberg in Bjork 2010, II.604), and Peter Dear observes that 'experience' does not so much designate "a fundamental, unproblematic way of acquiring knowledge (sensory experience as a form of knowledge)" but "has since the 1970s at least been regarded by philosophers of science as constituted and ordered by prior conceptual categories. 'Experience', in this view, depends on the expectations and presumptions of the observer" (Dear 2006, 108). In a nutshell, the semantic around ideas of 'experience and experimentation' has created serious problems of cultural and historical mis-translation. Whenever we are confronted with terms belonging to the semantic field of experientia and experimentum, we—as modern, culturally situated readers—are only too willing to project our own, distinctly modern understanding of experience and experimentation back in time, only to find predictable evidence for some form of 'incipient modern empiricism' and emerging ideas of 'modern interiority and subjectivity' (see further Fiorentino 2015). As Mark Barker observed in his 2012 study of Thomas Aquinas's use of experientia and experimentum, "[t]o define experientia as 'the testing of possibilities' retrojects a modern understanding of tests as the search for possibilities as such into the premodern mindset. [...] Such a definition runs counter to the common-sense understanding of 'test' in ancient and medieval ordinary language. [...] Overlooking this leads to the translation of ancient and medieval texts as if they had been authored by protomoderns." (Barker 2012, 44–5).

Some typical examples of this kind of mistranslation can be found in a range of influential historiographical accounts from the mid twentieth century. Historians often interpreted the 'precocious' interest in experimentation in scholastic culture - especially among English authors — as heralding the emergence of more fully developed ideas of modern empirical or 'experimental' science, postulating a direct line connecting medieval English authors such as Grosseteste, Roger Bacon, John Peckham, and William of Ockham with post-medieval British thinkers who have been instrumental in the development of modern empiricism, including Francis Bacon, Thomas Hobbes, John Locke, George Berkeley and David Hume (Butterfield 1949; Crombie 1953).

Herbert Butterfield, *The Origins of Modern Science, 1300–1800*. London: Bell & Sons, 1949

(Alistair C. Crombie, *Robert Grosseteste and the Origins of Experimental Science, 1100-1700*. Oxford: Clarendon Press ; 1953)

But a closer look at actual scholastic writings and debates suggests a very different picture.

So, to sum up, my point is that both Langland and Chaucer are demonstrably interested in the imaginative and psychological processes involved in 'experience', but that they do not really define what experience is. If anything, instead of trying to answer the question about the mechanics and truth-value of 'experience', they raise a range of ever more complex questions about the problem. Clearly neither Langland nor Chaucer believe 'experience' to be unproblematic or scientifically reliable in the modern, empirical sense...

This is entirely in keeping with the developments in contemporary intellectual culture. I would love to go into more detail here, but in the interest of time I need to synthesise, and I simply want to make three quite general points.

1) First: in medieval scholastic Latin both *experientia* and *experimentum* — which are roughly equivalent terms until well into the XVI century — do not in fact refer to the methodology of experimental science, but rather to the psychological processes involved in the journey from sense perception to cognition. They designate mental, not empirical phenomena, let alone something like an empirical method. This is in many ways unsurprising, since as Peter King observes (perhaps a bit bluntly but accurately) 'the method of medieval science was thought-experiment rather than actual experiment or testing' (King 1991, 43).

2) Second point: fourteenth-century thinkers in particular - building on the foundations of Neo-Aristotelian Faculty psychology as developed during the previous century, on the back of the 'rediscovery of Aristotle's *De Anima* and the work of Arabic commentators - become embroiled in a whole series of prolonged, and largely unresolved (perhaps insoluble?) disputes over the epistemic value of experience. Part of the debate concerns whether sensory experience is reliable, in what circumstances, but also the question of whether experience is a passive or an active process, or a mix of the two and to what degree. There is also disagreement concerning the relative role of the external senses, the internal senses in the sensitive soul (from 3 to 5 according to the model one adopts), or the intellectual soul - further subdivided into those rather mysterious entities, or perhaps function,

that came to be designated as the agent intellect and the passive or potential intellect following Aristotle's *De Anima*. A further question concerns the 'ontology' of the primary object of experience - with most scholastics agreeing that the mind cognises not objects directly, but only does so through a variety of mediating instances whose ontological status is fundamentally unclear...

This really is an inheritance of Aristotle's famous 'semantic Triangle' - an absolutely fundamental point of reference not only for the Neo-Aristotelian Psychology of the scholastics, but also for the tradition of terminist semantics and speculative grammar. The passage is really about the relations between objects, concepts in the mind, and words we use to designate objects - by means of the mediating concepts. The problem is essentially concept formation...

The - De Interpretatione (Periermenias, 16a3-9):

Now spoken sounds are symbols of affections in the soul, and written marks symbols of spoken sounds. And just as written marks are not the same for all men, neither are spoken sounds. But what these are in the first place signs of—affections of the soul—are the same for all; and what these affections are likenesses of—actual things—are also the same. These matters have been discussed in the work on the soul and do not belong to the present subject [cf. De anima, III.5-8];

*In fact, nearly all scholastics agreed that what the mind cognises not the object in the real world itself (the *res extra*), but some form of mediating entity - and here a bewildering forest of concepts are invoked, from the species to other concepts that are sometimes felt to be roughly synonymous with species, and which are endowed with 'diminished being' (*esse diminutum*), such *intentio*, *imago*, *phantasma*, *ydolum*, *simulacrum*, or even a *mental verbum*. The question of the ontological status of these mediating instances was particularly vexed, and in most of the later theories developed from about 1320s onwards, scholastics increasingly accepted that such instances were produced not so by the object itself, but rather by the mind of the perceiver. So Pater Auriol famously coins the controversial notion of *esse apparens* (apparent being), which he argues is the primary object of perception; even Ockham in his early thought submits that the object of perception is nothing other than a *fictum* — a fictional, fabricated entity. According to most theories from this period, then, what we cognise are concepts (in the modern sense of the term) - not things.*

In his later thought Ockham of course does away with any such mediating instances, and argues that the mind cognises the object itself directly ('direct realism that presupposes action at a distance'); but this theory of direct realism is a lone voice in the wilderness (it is fundamentally at odds with Aristotle's physics), and none of Ockham's successors accept this solution — and this is only one of the many reasons why postulating an influence of Ockhamist ideas upon Chaucer is historically difficult to substantiate.

But let's leave Ockham alone... because my main point is quite simply that fourteenth-century scholasticism is characterised by wide disagreements and lively debates concerning both the mechanics of sensory experience and its epistemic value.

3) A third point: English poetry from the later fourteenth century is characterised a particularly strong interest in ideas of experience and the associated mental processes - but this is not the beginning of the story. Yes, scholastic debates did (perhaps) play a role in focusing attention on this question (in ways that are mostly very difficult to trace...), but the question of experience already looms pretty large in the earlier literary tradition of French allegorical dream vision narratives. In particular, two key texts stand out - both widely read, debated, and adapted in late fourteenth and early fifteenth century England, namely the *Roman de la Rose* itself (the 'seminal' text of this tradition..), and the allegorical *Pèlerinages* of the Cistercian Guillaume de Deguileville. I suggest that these two works - together with a cluster

of further texts that move in the same orbit, such as Boethius's *Consolation of Philosophy* or some of the Latin philosophical poems from the twelfth century, by Alain de Lille and co. — play an extremely important role in facilitating the 'experiential turn' of English poetry in the late fourteenth century - this is something I have discussed in my latest book, discussing also the influence of this tradition on Langland very specifically.

So I just want to exemplify what this emerging interest in experience looks like in a couple of salient extracts

> *Contreres choses*

> *Viellece*

I want to focus on just a couple of passages, where both the Rose and Deguileville insist on the centrality of personal 'experience' as a source of knowledge - implying rather strongly that experience may be a rather more compelling source of knowledge than textual auctoritee, and specifically more veridical than logical argumentation (topical or demonstrative), which is traditionally viewed as the primary method through which 'scientific' knowledge is produced in the Aristotelian tradition (this is scientia in the medieval sense, so the idea that syllogistic reasoning is 'scientific' in the sense of faciens scire, it is 'productive of (true) knowledge - and it has really very little to do with modern, empiricist ideas of science).

Both texts then extol the virtues of experientia to some degree - although clearly there are serious differences too. The narrator in the Rose understands the virtues of 'experience' as an almost epicurean call to throw oneself at the world, to multiply pleasures and pains, as the only gateway to real 'connoissance' - this, at the very least is what the most unreliable narrator tells us... and it is anybody's guess whether this really is the 'bottom line' moral of the poem, or merely yet another of the countless number of divergent truths that are crammed into the poem... Regardless, the point does occupy a highly prominent position in the poem, and is meant to stand as some sort of 'diffinitive sentence' in it, regardless of the degree of irony...

For Deguileville, experientia develops a more strongly 'penitential' character - although I want to stress that this 'penitential' idea is not entirely absent from the Rose either, although Jean de Meun does not draw out the penitential resonances explicitly.

I am not going to discuss the Langlandian 'continuities' of these two passages, except for identifying the passages that follow on directly from his french intertexts here...

I'm not going to look at Chaucer at all in terms of his 'response' to this, but my overall point is that Chaucer too intervenes in this conversation to reflect on the nature of experience.

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Now I'd love to illustrate what I'm saying with some examples and close readings - but again you need to rely on some generalisations in the interest of time. What is striking about both the *Rose* and Deguileville's *Pèlerinages* is not only that they focus rather insistently on the question of experience, but that they already do so in a distinctly exploratory and interrogative mode. What I mean by that is that neither of those two poems ultimately succeeds in **defining** the nature experience or the epistemic status of experiential knowledge: much as in the writings of their scholastic contemporaries, there appears to be a lack of consensus about the actual mechanics of experience, its psycho-physiological mechanisms, and its truth-value.

*Perhaps it is worth adding that whereas neither poem **succeeds** in doing this, the Rose does not even appear to try, and Jean de Meun (who knew a thing or two about scholastic methods) seems to enjoy nothing more than bringing into play conflicting and mutually contradictory theoretical models of mind and sensation and imagination. Deguileville on the other hand DOES try, but rather miserably fails, and ends up creating what is a pretty serious muddle by borrowing from a whole range of largely incompatible theories of mind, both Augustinian and Aristotelian with a good dose of Avicenna. The result is that in the very attempt to clarify the nature of mental operations involved in producing experiential knowledge he creates even more confusion and uncertainty...*

To make a rather complex and potentially very long story rather short, it is to these French poems that we need to look if we are trying to explain the otherwise seemingly 'sudden' experiential turn of English poetry in the generation of Langland and Chaucer.

In my recent work I have often been arguing that all of these texts — from the *Rose*, to Deguileville, to Langland and Chaucer's dream visions — not only constitute a literary tradition, but that they all use first-person dream poetry for distinctly philosophical or speculative purposes. For these authors, dream vision poetry almost functions as an extended and open-ended thought experiment in narrative form, and I have insisted on the intellectually enabling, heuristic, and exploratory nature of this kind of allegorical narrative. More specifically, I have argued that these texts are ultimately all concerned, in some fundamental fashion, to explore the problem of experience, and a wide range of associated problems that crystallise on the back of the broadly Neo-Aristotelian Psychology that dominates the scholastic period.

But ... I am also beginning to wonder whether my claim that Dream-vision allegory is used for purposes of philosophical speculation isn't a little too enthusiastic and optimistic perhaps. After all, there are plenty of pretty 'conventional', derivative, and rather uninspired poems in this tradition, especially in the much-maligned fifteenth century... One thing that is beginning to emerge for me is that after the 'rise' of an experiential poetics in the generation of Chaucer and Langland, we might have to allow for a 'fall'... I don't want to prejudge the issue, but it seems to me that while the notion of experience remains an important feature of later texts in this tradition, there appears to be a shift in the attitude towards experience, characterised by greater caution and even ambivalence. Later poems in this tradition seem less adventurous, less exploratory, and less comfortable with posing genuinely philosophical questions that may not have an easy answer. Perhaps there even is a shift in how the very notion of 'experience' is understood.

In any case, dream vision allegory is no longer used to facilitate open-ended intellectual speculation, but rather to **constrain** that very speculation, to regulate and channel it into a very specific direction that boils down to much more rigid,

normative ideas about the function and limitations of personal experience in relation to other sources of knowledge - particularly *auctoritee*. This, at least, is what seems to happen with the text I want to focus on for the remainder of this paper - the Middle English R&S.

Dated to about 1410, often attributed to Lydgate although the attribution is disputed by some (I am pretty sure it is Lydgate's). This poem is a translation of a French source that already looks back to the RR - the French *Eschez amoureux*, dated to 1370s - and perhaps the work of Evrart De Conty, who is also the author of an extended moralising commentary on the *Eschez Amoureux*. Because we have 3 stages, it becomes possible to trace some sort of progression, that in my opinion describes this movement **away** from the pretty radical speculative open-endedness of the *Rose*.

Let me first provide a very rough summary of the *EA*, before comparing the French source with its English translation.

The *acteur* is in a typical spring setting, and encounters dame Nature, **SLIDE 5** who presents him with the choice of two paths, each of them associated with a specific form of knowledge: the path of **Reason & Understandinge**, which assimilates man with the divine; and the path of **vertu sensityf** - essentially knowledge relying on the input from the external senses. He moves on and, encounters three goddesses Venus, Juno, or Pallas, and he has to essentially repeat the Judgment of Paris; of course he goes for Venus... He then meets Diana, who chastises him for his bad choice. He persists in his loyalty to Venus, and eventually arrives in the Garden of Déduit, and he observes how the Garden corresponds exactly to the details found in the earlier description of this place in the RR **quote 6**: *Oisense, the God of love with his arrows, the fountain of Narcissus, etc.* The *acteur* now witnesses a game of Chess between a Lady and Deduis, which the Lady wins. It is now the turn of the *acteur* to play against the lady; the chess-pieces are now described, and allegorised, but this however is where the English translation breaks off, before the match can begin . **20 MINS** We are only 5000 lines into the poem (over 30'000 *vers*...), but the remainder of EA can be summarised pretty quickly: the *acteur* eventually loses his game; he pays homage to the God of Love; is given a thorough instruction in the art of Love by Cupid; Cupid departs, and Pallas arrives on the scene. Predictably, Pallas talks up the excellence of the contemplative life, which she embodies - at the expense of the active life (Juno), and the voluptuous life (Venus). Strikingly, however, Pallas's long lecture (over 15'000 verses..) also contains a wealth of useful practical instruction about governance, family management, and the active life in the secular sphere more generally,... and in fact her lecture draws extensively on Giles of Rome's *de Regimine Principum*.

So, while it is fair to say that EA is a poem that, like many others, is grounded in a broadly moralised reading of the RR (condemning voluptuous living and analysing

the dangers of erotic infatuation...), it can't really be said that the French poem dismisses any secular values and the active life altogether. *Vita activa* is, up to a point, a legitimate form of living.. even if it falls short of the perfections of *vita contemplativa*. This makes for an interesting, complex, nuanced, and perhaps not entirely coherent ideological project for this poem...

RS clearly inherits the broadly moral slant of the original EA, but arguably sharpens any condemnation of eroticism. I'd love to exemplify this - and have a mass of 'evidence' - but there just isn't enough time...

What I am really interested in, however, is that the two poems represent the **experience of erotic desire** in subtly different ways, assigning very different value and significance to this experience. To be more exact, I would like to examine the two poems in terms of their handling of the competing claims of *experience* and *auctoritee*.... *experientia* and *auctoritas*. This tension, while not entirely absent from the French poem, becomes a real concern in the English translation... which (unlike its source) comes down rather firmly on the side of *auctoritas* and against experience...

I want to start by identifying some very broad changes made in the translation, before focusing on its discussion of experience very specifically.

- Firstly, the English RS contains a wealth of references to its source. 'as myn auctor tellys' RS 933; 'as seyth my boke' RS 1030; ' the booke seyth thus' RS 1035. This highlights the English poem's status as a translation, and reminds us that the poem's narrator/translator is NOT, or no longer, identical with the fictional *acteur*... This places the visionary experience at one remove from the poet, and at two removes from the reader, emphasising the 'literariness' and textual genealogy of the English poem...
- Second, there are also a wealth of general references to unspecified writings of other clerks, poets, and *auctores*: 'as clerkes wryte / And in her bookes lyst endyte ' RS 1037-8; 'Rede poetys and ye shal se' RS 1051; 'As poetys specyfye' RS 1612; 'poetis pleynly write thus' RS 1645; 'olde poetys wryten so' RS 1755. None of this is in the source, and again, this lends the whole poem a greater sense of 'bookishness': we realise that we are not so much reading the account of 'raw' lived personal experience, but that such an experience has been collated against a wealth of learned sources, particularly mythographic, encyclopaedic, and exemplary ones. It is these sources, these other books, that, as it were, lend 'meaning' (*senefiance*) to the actual events...
- Which brings me to my next, third point... On the whole, the translation is far more 'exegetical' or 'explicative' than the original. It is didactic and exemplaristic where the original is more descriptive, leisurely, and allusive... The translator often takes on the task of unpacking the *senefiance* of various exemplary narratives at some length in the main text, and no longer relies

only on Latin marginalia to achieve this (as was the case in the original). Also, the poem now includes some direct appeals to the reader by the narrator - again something that we do not find in the original...where this kind of 'lecturing' only happens between the fictional characters (Nature, Pallas, Diana) and the hapless *acteur* — and this instructional dimension is again considerably expanded in the translation.

25 MINS

Despite this increased emphasis on the importance of allegorical exposition in RS, the *acteur* - just like Amant in the RR - shown little interest in the 'integumentis aus poetes' and remains a stubbornly literal reader. In QUOTE 7 he says 'I have no intention of seeking out the Golden Fleece like Jason, or to fly across the sea like Icarus...' and in the process completely misses the *moralitee* of these tales, used by Diana to try and dissuade him from following Venus...

I'm particularly interested in what happens next in this passage — especially in the English translation, which considerably intensifies the idea: the reason the *acteur* has no interest in such moral exempla is that he is far too interested in natural phenomena - and Kellie Robertson has explored the underlying discomfort with *Scientia Naturalis* that pervades the English poem in her book, a reading that dovetails very nicely with my own...

QUOTE 7a:

Not only is this more insistent, but it invites readers to put a more clearly negative spin on the *acteur*'s *curiositas* - QUOTE 7b: I'm rather struck by the statement that "reson out I wolde fynde / After the course oonly of kynde". This to me implies a rather mechanistic or 'physicalistic' kind of naturalism that we are meant to disapprove of. The implication is that it is not through 'empirical experience', but through moral and allegorical exposition that we obtain valuable, and especially *viable* knowledge.

COGNITION (internal senses)

This newly intensified epistemological concern with the relative value of different types of knowledge also produces a more extended discussion of mental processes, about the mechanics of perception, cognition, deliberation/judgement/assent. And much of this points to an exacerbated anxiety about erroneous judgement, especially when the latter is primarily determined by sensory input. You could say that the poem identifies the dangers of a passive, physicalistic and deterministic model of cognition, where the mind is literally 'inscribed' or 'imprinted' by sensory experiences (*this roughly corresponds to the stoic theory of cognition as outlined in Boethius' Consolation of Philosophy Bk V, m4*). And it is precisely this semantic field of 'imprinting' that is used in the translation to warn us against the dangers of *vertu*

sensitif— and this idea, and the motif of cognitive 'imprinting', is entirely absent from the source...

So, prudent Women are identified as those who are able to resist the 'imprinting' of 'sugared words' in their hearts (in a passage that is added wholesale to the source): both **QUOTE 8**

A further passage (also original in the translation) is less optimistic about female resistance to 'imprinting' of this kind, and again uses the same vocabulary **QUOTE 8** again:

*An interesting occurrence was already cited, as part of the acteur's speech where he refuses to engage in the kind of allegorical reading recommended by Diana, and reaffirms instead his desire to seek knowledge about natural phenomena **QUOTE 7**. There, at the very end of the passage, he mentions that*

***I ha this effeccion
Prentyd in myn oppinion,
RS 4611-23***

*The idea here is perhaps less directly about the mind being determined by sensory 'impression', and more about a mental fixation: the determination to seek knowledge about natural phenomena is indelibly imprinted, or 'set' in his mind, determining his belief (*opinio*)*

30 MINS

In all three cases this form of imprinting has clearly negative associations, the implication being that it ought to be resisted or avoided altogether.

But there are some positive counterexamples: the idea is that the mind can be advantageously shaped, and literally 'informed', but this time not by sensory input but rather by means of moral teachings conveyed through verbal or textual instruction. Take this example in the description of the arms of Pallas, where the reader (and not the acteur) is told by the translator to **emprynte in your memorye** the allegorical exposition he is about to provide **QUOTE 9**

Now because there are both positive and negative forms of imprinting, the mind requires careful policing and a solid second-order response. Take this other example, it is the opening speech by Diana, who points out to the *acteur* that he has been duped by Venus, and should reconsider his choice, based on erroneous judgement. **QUOTE 10a**: The instructional tone, and the discussion of role played by the imaginative faculty is not entirely absent from EA - but the English version really lays it on pretty thick, **QUOTE 10a**: with a much greater emphasis on the

problem of erroneous judgement - and also makes a rather different point. There is a lot of rather anxious emphasis, it seems to me, about the cognitive and deliberative / adjudicative processes involved in forming opinion and producing assent, and the point really is that the *acteur* should trust not sensory impression but rather the words of Diana (who is trying to 'enfourmen' the *acteur* by 'preching' to him). The point of the French; by contrast, is much more along the lines of: 'you're not going to listen to me anyway... so just go ahead and you will find out for yourself that I was right'... In the French experience will validate the instruction; in the English, the *acteur* is urged to avoid that experience altogether... because Diana's 'sermon' already gives him all the knowledge and information he needs (!!)

In general, then, it seems that forms of imprinting based on sensory input are generally negative, while 'good' imprinting generally has its origins in some verbal lesson and moral instruction.

*Cut here if no time... Skip QUOTES 12-13 All in all, then, RS is pervaded by an underlying sense of anxiety about the **deceptiveness of appearances** (RS 2250, 3169, 3206)— something the EA is much more sanguine about, and does not identify as a major theme.*

Take this passage, the end of Mercury's extended speech about the three Goddesses (Pallas June and Venus) and the *acteur*'s need to make his choice
QUOTE 11:

The English translation is full of rather agonised technical description of the decision-making process — and there really is none of this in the original French: there is a simple question. I also find it rather amusing how the passage he simultaneously emphasises the *acteur*'s free will ('thou hauest lyberte', and yet simultaneously reminds him that such 'lyberte' ought to be informed 'by counsayl and rede of me'; again, the emphasis is on verbal instruction and mental deliberation - not on sensory input and perception...

*The most striking example for this perhaps occurs when the Goddess Diana seeks to reveal to the *acteur* that his choice of Venus is based precisely on the erroneous assumption that her pleasing aspect denotes a positive, virtuous moral disposition - again turning what is a passing comment in EA into a laborious scrutiny of epistemic processes **QUOTE 12:***

Comment on 'repenting'... as 'make amends', 'make penitence', 'relinquish'...

*The question of the disjunction between sensory experience and internal 'doom' or judgement (or 'assent', to use the technical term..) is developed throughout the exchange that follows. Where the *acteur* in EA simply states that on the basis of experience to date there is nothing untoward to report about Venus (*je n' ay encore trouvé, De tant que j' en ay esprouvé, Fors que tout bien*), RS again develops at length and more technically **QUOTE 13:***

Clearly the passage in the translation goes out of its way to underline the problematic epistemic status of 'proof' and 'experience', and in fact points to the **insufficiency of experience** unaided by some form of higher guidance and correction - which is readily provided, of course, by Diana, and (implicitly) by the poet, with his tendency to inflate any expository, interpretive, and didactic impetus that is often merely implicit in the text of the EA or in its marginal Latin glosses. Notice also how insistently Diana emphasises the crucial role of instruction in her opening couplet: "My faire frende, yif thou hyst **lere**, / Somwhat of Venus thou shalt **here**" here the rhyme '**lere/here**' really visualises the idea that knowledge is inextricably tied up with 'hearing and listening' to moral instruction rather than simply relying on the supposed 'proof' derived from sensory experience and — all too readily misconstrued in the 'fantasy' of the perceiver / acteur...

It is symptomatic therefore that RS (unlike EA) is constantly preoccupied with drawing our attention to the unstable and uncertain nature of 'opinion' - a term that is used 13 times in RS (e.g. also 5983), and only once in the corresponding section of EA. RS is therefore not only more interested in epistemological matters, but also far more anxious, and perhaps 'sceptical' about the processing of sensory information in the mind and the formation of judgements...

Short to here is no time... All in all, then, RS is pervaded by an underlying sense of anxiety about the **deceptiveness of appearances** (RS 2250, 3169, 3206)— something the EA is much more sanguine about, and does not identify as a major theme.

EXPERIENCE

So far everything I've been saying suggests that in comparison to its source, RS is a poem that is far from comfortable with the idea of empirical, sensory 'experience' in general. This does not mean that the vocabulary of experience disappears from the translation - on the contrary; if anything, this concern with experience is more, not less prominent in the translation.

The reason for this is not only that RS works so hard to disqualify or discredit the value of 'experience', but it also effectively **transforms and redefines** the meaning of 'experience' altogether.

Let me illustrate how this happens and then I'll wrap up

This is a short snippet from the speech given by the God Mercury as he prepares to restage the judgement of Paris. Quite apart from the shift from the fairly neutral and descriptive tone of EA to the more sententious and schoolmasterly tone of RS, the English translation also introduces the idea of proof or 'euydence'

QUOTE 14:

But such 'euydence' is not at all provided by empirical testing or sensory experience of some sort, but by means of verbal exposition: **I shal yive the euydence, First expovne... Of alle the mater, how hit stood**

35 MINS

Another revealing discussion of experience in this sense, is the following. This comes from the condemnation of Venus contained in Diana's speech: **QUOTE 15a**

The point is: Experience will teach you that Venus is like the monstrous *Chimera*. You can see that the mention of the Chimera is already there in the source, but RS **QUOTE 15a** introduces the idea that this figure provides the reader with 'experience' of the dangers of eros. But in what sense is the 'experience' of desire comparable to the chimera - a fantastical beast that we certainly do not encounter in the realm of 'experience'? The point is, rather, that the moral exposition of the chimera will give us insight into the nature of desire as it could be (hypothetically) experienced in the real world. Again, the source of wisdom is not experience itself - which is pleasurable and deceptive - but Diana's exposition, which in the source is merely a marginal Latin gloss but here is incorporated into the main body of the text...

Something very similar happens with another mythical beast, the Siren RS 3641-54, and with the description of 'serpentys and dragouns', all of them supposedly found in the Garden of Cupid: "**And who abytt her eny while, / He shal haue experyence / Of ther cruel violence**" (RS 3910-13).

Here experience describes at best the formation of an opinion or idea on the basis of a mental image that has no physical substance at all... Significantly, such marvellous beasts exist only in **books**, and not in reality. More generally, then, the English poem associates proof not so much with empirical experience, but with various forms of textual or literary 'evidence' that is used to visualise a moral lesson: **'Examples preve** it more than oon', RS 4161 says Diana (in a passage where the source uses neither proof nor exemplum... *EA 3241-3*).

To sum up my points so far: RS makes a distinct effort to foreground the importance of instruction, literary tradition, exemplary narratives, and carefully constructed mental images with a moral/allegorical meaning **at the expense of** actual experience.

BUT there's a snag - and it's a big one... the problem is that this logic runs contrary to the spirit of the original French poem. In fact, the whole poem is really predicated on the injunction to the acteur, pronounced by Nature herself, that he should go out into the world and seek knowledge — and more specifically self-knowledge. **QUOTE 16:**

Interestingly, the English translation replaces this incentive to study natural phenomena (*Adfin que matere y comprendes*) and to seek self-knowledge (*De ta grant dignité congnoistre, / Et que tu le puissez accroistre*) with a penitential injunction (thy selfe to amende) and a more pedestrian 'fro vycis to restraine'.

Whereas the source invites an **exploratory** posture (study the natural world and know thyself), the translation is much more strongly **prescriptive, moralistic, and penitential...**

This injunction to 'go out and see the world' is later picked up by the acteur, to counter Diana's advice that he should take up the life of a hermit: **QUOTE 17** :

The differences again are subtle but striking: in EA the emphasis falls in equal measure on the sensory appeal and on the desire for scientific knowledge of natural phenomena: '**la beaulté**' but also '**cognoistre**' - and the implication is that both pleasure and scientific knowledge are, up to a point, legitimate, 'natural' pursuits... In RS, by contrast, the description is almost exclusively focused on the sensory or rather sensual appeal of nature, subtly nudging the reader to buy into the moralising disapproval of this kind of harmful, illegitimate curiosity. Notice also the use of '**privetee**', loaded with Chaucerian echoes, and clearly used disapprovingly here...

But to return to my main point: there is a tension here between the fact that the poem we start with (the EA) that values experience, and embraces the idea that one should seek practical, empirical confirmation of traditional teaching in practice. This idea is to some extent hard-wired into the narrative, flowing from Nature's initial injunction to go out into the world and seek such knowledge (of whatever kind..). But RS - a poem that by necessity inherits this narrative direction - is a poem that in many ways seeks to evade direct experience.

In some sense, the translator is quite simply uncomfortable with the overarching experiential and exploratory premise of the poem he has chosen to translate. The translator makes a consistent effort to suppress and overwrite this - but the idea really is hard-wired into the poem, and the result is a rather conflicted text that does not quite work... and this may explain why the surviving translation is unfinished.; an abortive project.

Now, to reconnect with the beginning of my paper, and with the larger idea that the tradition of the *Roman de la Rose* is characterised by a strongly 'experiential' and 'exploratory' momentum... As we've seen the EA is a poem that clearly presupposes the reader's familiarity with the *Rose*, and in fact presents itself as a response or rewriting of JdM's poem. But on closer inspection things are actually more interesting, because the *acteur* not only finds himself in an imaginary landscape that is reminiscent of the RR, but **recognises** this fact. In short, he

observes that his experiences **reproduce and replicate** — and thereby **validate** the events related by the earlier poem (**quote 6**):

Nothing special perhaps, as many other poems feature dreams that implicitly or explicitly refer to the experience of reading the 'biau Roman de la Rose' (both Chaucer's *Book of the Duchess*...Deguileville's *Pèlerinage de l'âme*). But what happens in the EA (and the RS) is rather different, because we are NOT in fact in a dream at all...

40 MINS

The EA in fact is an account of a waking vision - and this is a point that is made clearly and insistently at the start of the poem **quote 18**:

The point here is that this is a waking vision, perhaps in the manner of Boethius's *Consolation* - an idea that is picked up again in the *Commentary to the EA*, the EAM, authored by Evrart de Conty **quote 19**:

Nous avons donc quant a ce premier point .iii. manieres de faindre: l' une par revelacion d' un mort resuscité, **l' autre par maniere de songe et l' autre par ymaginaire vision. Et par ceste tierce maniere parle l' aucteur** du livre rimé dessusdit dont nous voulons parler, quant il faint que Nature se vint a moustrer a ly, **par quoy il vould pretendre que ceste vision reele qui des yeulx corporeulx se feist** a la lectre ainz fut tant seulement ymaginee telle.¹

I take this to mean - as do the editors of the poem - that the narrative of the EA has a higher truth-value than the Dream Vision of the RR. In fact, I would like to suggest that the EA very deliberately presents the experiences of its own *acteur* as a sort of validation and confirmation of the veracity of the reported dream that makes up the earlier poem by GdL and JdM.

But this experiential emphasis is precisely what troubles the translator.... who makes one further, and rather radical attempt to 'defuse' this by modifying the macro-structure of the poem. Remember that the poem starts out **as a waking vision** and not as a dream, but... the English translation very quickly, and almost imperceptibly slides back into the more conventional mode of the dream. This becomes clear in two passages: **quote 20**:

It seems the translator has now changed his mind... and we are not - or no longer - reading an account of a first-person protagonist's ostensibly real-life waking

¹ Evrart de Conty, *EAM*, 9^v44–10^r2, p.24.

experience.... Rather (just as in Chaucer's *Book of the Duchess*) we are reading the account of events that have merely been 'dreamt up'.

This move - and it strikes me as a highly deliberate choice, especially in the second extract - has again a distancing, defamiliarising effect upon the reader. Of course we can still think ourselves into the fiction... but we are aware that it is already **imagined and not experienced** by the *acteur* (who in any case is NOT identical with the English translator who repeatedly reminds us that he is transcribing the book of 'myn auctour... who sayth thus'). And we suddenly find ourselves at two removes from the action (or is it three?). It is in the truest sense a thought experiment - not an experience we are invited to analyse, and let alone reproduce in our own real waking lives. The subtext is: stay away from the Garden of Deduit...no point in looking further, because this book here, containing a reported dream that in turn reiterates the ostensibly moral injunctions of the *Rose*, tells you all you need to know about it.

If this is true, then the two poems are actually making a very different point about *experience* and *auctoritee* despite their extremely close similarities. So to conclude for good....

> The EA seems to be telling us that no amount of poetic description of the realities of erotic desire can replace the experience itself. Yes, of course there is already a vast available archive of wisdom and moral instruction to tell us about the dangers of erotic desire... But no matter how truthful and persuasive this might all be, each individual is eventually bound to seek out a personal experience of desire and of nature, out there in the real world - even if only to validate such pre-existing truth and wisdom. Any existing accounts and descriptions of erotic desire preserved in the collective literary archive are useful, but can only ever function as gloss or blueprint for an individual, lived personal experience, whose details, contradictions, twists and turns and surprises are unique, even if they loosely conform to an existing pattern - such as the one given by the *Romance of the Rose*. *Experience* and *auctoritee* are complementary, they go hand in hand, 'contreres choses, les unes des autres gloses'.

> RS, however, explodes this dialecticism between experience and auctoritee. The translation invites us to distance ourselves from this protagonist - who really is reduced to the exemplary embodiment of a 'fol amoureux', as is the case in many other moralised responses to the RR. Now that the events are being put back 'inside the box' of a dream, as it were, they are more easily kept at a distance. We are witnessing an exemplary **but also imaginary** tale of perdition. The implication is that the author does NOT expect, let alone encourage his readers to actually venture out into the 'real world' to experience the lures of 'Sensuality' for themselves, but rather to rely on an exemplary tale that allows us to experience such dangers vicariously. It is as though the *acteur* is having, or rather dreaming up,

conjuring up this fictional experience of desire **for us..**, on our behalf.... so we don't have to. All that is left for us to do, is to sit back and perform the work of allegorical interpretation and moralisation that the protagonist himself refuses to, or is unable to, take on.

This is hardly evidence for the continuing 'rise' of an experiential poetics in late medieval England (as I perhaps foolishly assumed when I started this project...). Rather than functioning as a script that could help us to meaningfully organise our own experiences in the real world, R&S proposes itself as a **surrogate** for an experience we should seek to avoid altogether.